

Measurement of HF Monopole Antenna Array Ground Wave Gain, Antenna Factor, and Antenna Noise Factor

by

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Abstract

This paper presents a practical way to measure the ground wave gain G_{GW} , ground wave antenna factor AF_{GW} , and antenna noise factor $F_a(Mon)$ of monopoles used in HF antenna arrays. It shows measurement results taken from June 1997 to September 1999 at five geographically separated HF arrays. $F_a(Mon)$ is derived from site specific noise electric field E_n and can be compared with "standard" $F_a(*)$. While antenna noise factor is antenna dependent, E_n is not and can be used as a limit for site EMC with noise emitters.

Background

Over the past 20 years or so, we have used standard 9-ft rod antennas to measure the antenna noise factor F_a [1] of HF sites and compared the site electromagnetic noise environment with published F_a [2,3,4]. While this method is accepted as scientifically valid and conforms to standards, it only applies to the performance of 9-ft rod antennas, and may not necessarily describe the performance of operational HF monopole antennas. Hence, the author developed a method for measuring the as-installed, site-specific ground wave gain, ground wave antenna factor, and antenna noise factor that applies to operational HF antennas.

The US military uses circularly disposed antenna arrays with monopole elements for HF direction finding (HFDF) applications. One family of these arrays is designated the AN/FRD-13, which employs a "high band" array consisting of 24 6-meters high monopoles arranged 15 degrees apart in a 25-meter radius circle.

In this paper, the measurement process involves three distinct steps:

- Determining the site specific ground wave gain G_{GW} ,
- Calculating the ground wave antenna factor AF_{GW} , which is the ratio of the external electric field intensity to the antenna output voltage, and

- Measuring the antenna noise factor using noise samples from site monopoles and the previously obtained G_{GW} and AF_{GW} .

Derivation of the expressions for these parameters follow.

Ground Wave Gain and Ground Wave Antenna Factor Measurement

This section presents a derivation of the equation and process for measuring the G_{GW} of monopole antennas. To measure this parameter, one must generate a ground wave signal with a transmit monopole, propagate this signal to a receive monopole, measure the transmission loss, and use the expressions below to calculate G_{GW} . The process is simplified by using identical monopoles that are situated within line of sight, but far enough to be in the radiating far field region [5,6]. Literature defines this region as the distance where error due to wavefront phase differences is less than 10% or where the radiated wave impedance approaches 377 ohms. Figures 1 and 2 below shows the measurement set up and the distances between monopoles in a 25 meter radius circularly disposed antenna array.

Figure 1. Measurement set up.

Figure 2. Minimum radiating far field distance “Beta” and distance between test array monopoles.

At each test site, the author injected a +10 dBm swept frequency signal into an arbitrarily selected “transmit” monopole, then measured the output power at a second monopole. Readings at the test frequencies of 2.5, 5.0, 7.5, 10, 20, and 30 MHz were recorded during the measurements using the equipment markers. Seven pairs of monopoles 43.3 meters apart were used to calculate a median G_{GW} .

Using the familiar Friis transmission equation, which describes the received power p_r at the output port of an antenna is [5,6]

$$p_r \square \frac{p_t g_t}{4 \square r^2} \frac{g_r \square^2}{4 \square} \quad (1)$$

where p_t and p_r are the received and transmitted power referenced to the antenna ports, g_t and g_r are the transmit and receive antenna gains respectively, \square is the transmit frequency wavelength, and r is the distance between the antennas. If $g_t = g_r = g_{gw}$, as is the case for the array monopoles, and the power measurement reference is shifted to the test equipment ports using the matched cable loss L_c , then Eq. 1 could be re-arranged to:

$$g_{gw} \square \sqrt{\frac{RF_{in} f_{MHz}^2 (4 \square r_m)^2}{RF_{out} l_c^2 300^2}} \quad (2)$$

or, in decibels:

$$G_{GW} = (RF_{in} - RF_{out})/2 - L_c + 10 \text{Log } F_{MHz} + 10 \text{Log } r_m - 13.78 \quad (3)$$

Figure 3. G_{GW} measurement results and median.

It can be noted that the term $(RF_{in} - RF_{out})$ is directly readable as S21 in a network analyzer and L_c could be normalized out during S21 test cable calibration.

A known limitation of this process is the fact that the ohmic and coupler losses of the antennas are included in the P_t and P_r terms. More accurate measurement techniques are discussed in literature using separate, calibrated monopole [7].

Measurement results seen in Figure 3 below show the differences among the test sites which could be due to the differences in ground constants and from reflections from an equipment hut located at the center of the array. The repeatability of the data between sites and in repeat visits, however, is well within ± 2 dB at all test frequencies. The author intends to measure ground constants in future efforts.

Ground Wave Antenna Factor Calculation

For a lossless antenna, the antenna factor can be calculated by equating the signal power captured by an antenna to the output port power. Hence,

$$\frac{e^2}{120 \square} \frac{g_r \square^2}{4 \square} \square \frac{v^2}{r_l} \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 could be re-arranged to solve for $f_a^2 = e^2/v^2$:

$$\frac{e^2}{v^2} \square \frac{480 \square^2}{g_r r_l \square^2} \quad (5)$$

which can be converted into decibels using Eq 6:

$$AF_{GW} \approx 20 \log_{10} f_{MHz} + G_r - 10 \log_{10} r_f - 12.79 \quad (6)$$

The terms $-10 \log_{10} r_f - 12.79$ becomes -31.5 for 75 ohm antennas, and -29.8 for 50 ohm antennas [1, p 26]. AF_{GW} for 6 m monopoles is shown below in Figure 4.

Figure 4. AF_{GW} for 6m monopoles calculated from Figure 3 data.

Antenna Noise Factor

The next section presents a derivation of a formula for the antenna noise factor, f_a , which is the ratio of the intercepted noise power to thermal noise power at room temperature.

$$f_a \approx \frac{P_n}{kT_0 b} \approx \frac{e_n^2 g_r}{120 \cdot 4 \cdot kT_0 b} \quad (7)$$

where $k = 1.38 \times 10^{-23}$ Joules, $T_0 = 288^\circ$ K, b is the bandwidth in Hertz. If e_n is in μ V, Eq. 7 could also be re-written in decibels (Eq 8) to represent f_a for any antenna with known gain g_r .

$$F_a \approx E_n \approx 20 \log_{10} f_{MHz} + 10 \log_{10} b + G_r - 96.8 \quad (8)$$

The terms $G_r + 96.8$ becomes 95.5 for short monopoles (standard 9-ft rods) and 98.8 for dipoles in free space [1, p48]. For the 6m monopoles, G_r is the G_{GW} , and E_n could be calculated from the spectrum analyzer data using Eq 9:

$$E_n = P_{ave} - 107 + K_{sa} + AF_{GW} - L_c \quad (9)$$

where P_{ave} is the minimum average power over a span that is $\pm 5\%$ of the test frequency, 107 converts power in dBm into voltage in dB μ V, k_{sa} is the manufacturer's logarithmic amplifier correction factor, AF_{GW} comes from Eq. 6, and L_c is the cable loss factor in decibels. Hence, F_a for 6m monopoles simplify into:

$$F_a(Mon) = P_{ave} + AF_{GW} - L_c + G_{GW} - 20 \log_{10}(f_{MHz}) - 10 \log_{10}(b_{Hz}) + 206.3 \quad (10)$$

If comparison to antenna factors for the standard 9-ft rod [2,3,4] is desired, then the measured 6m monopole P_{ave} data could also be used in the following expression to calculate $F_a(*)$

$$F_a(*) = P_{ave, dBm} + AF_{GW} - L_c - 20 \log_{10} f_{MHz} - 10 \log_{10} b_{Hz} + 205.0 \quad (11)$$

The reader is cautioned that Equations 10 and 11 are only valid for spectrum analyzers with $k_{sa} = 2.5$.

Noise Models

Electromagnetic noise models are generally presented in terms of 9-ft rod monopole antenna noise factors $F_a(*)$ as researchers in the past have used these antennas for convenience and standardization. It is important to note that while F_a is not the same for different antennas immersed in the same electric field, the noise electric field E_n is independent of antennas. Hence, the author uses the site noise electric field as a basis for performance comparisons between operational sites. The values of $F_a(*)$ at generic sites, as well as corresponding E_n can be calculated using Equations 12 and 13 respectively. The constants in these equations are shown in Table 1.

$$F_a(*) = k1a \log(FMHz) + k2a + 10 \log(b) \quad (12)$$

$$E_n(*) = k1e \log(FMHz) + k2e + 10 \log(b) \quad (13)$$

Table 1. Noise Model Constants

Model	Fa(9'Mon)		En	
	k1a	k2a	k1e	k2e
Business	-27.7	76.8	-7.7	-18.7
Residential	-27.7	72.5	-7.7	-23.0
Rural	-27.7	67.2	-7.7	-28.3
Quiet Rural	-28.6	53.6	-8.6	-41.9
Noisy	-37.5	83.2	-17.5	-12.3
Quiet	-29.1	65.2	-9.1	-30.3

Figure 5. US #1 suburban site.

Figures 5 to 9 shows the $F_a(Mon)$ and noise electric field E_n data measured from five array sites taken from June 1997 to September 1999. These figures also show the standard $F_a(*)$ for the site, plus "Quiet" and "Quiet Rural Area" noise models for 9-ft rod antennas [1,2,3,4]. Noise data samples were taken using at least 25 sweeps per test frequency, and from at least 6 monopoles spaced around the array.

Figure 7. Asia #2, suburban site.

In Figure 8, the high $F_a(Mon)$ from a third site in Asia at low frequencies were due to emissions from an uninterruptible power supply and from a digital modem installed in an equipment shelter located approximately 150 meters from the antenna array. The reduction of conducted noise in the shelter power leads and equipment shielded cables resulted in comparable radiated noise electric field reduction.

Figure 6. Asia #1, suburban site.

Figures 5, 6, and 7 contrast the noise at three sites in suburban environments. Elevation blockage to the antennas at the US #1 site was maintained at less than 5 degrees. At the ASIA #1 site, antennas were surrounded by 50-foot tall trees, which attenuated ground wave propagated man-made noise. High $E_n(max)$ observed at 10 MHz in the ASIA #1 site were due to high signal activities and intermodulation noise. Asia site #2 employs EMI control up to 2 km from the site.

Figure 8. Asia #3, rural site.

Both Figures 8 and 9 show very low variability in short term noise amplitudes, which can be expected from single-day measurement data. Data spread is more pronounced in multiple day measurements as those in Figures 5, 6, and 7. Table 2 presents summary data of the five site surveys.

Figure 9. European suburban site..

Spectrum Analyzer vs RMS Voltmeters

In obtaining the data for figures 5-9, the author used a spectrum analyzer in video average mode, and selected the minimum power for estimating the noise power. This method, coupled with the manufacturer supplied correction factor is comparable in accuracy to measurements using manually tuned r.m.s voltmeters. A comparison of the data taken with both types of instruments connected to a common antenna through a 1:2 power divider is shown below in Figure 10. The spectrum analyzer was set to average 22 traces, while 11 readings were taken at the same time with the r.m.s. voltmeter. The readings tracked within +1.7 to -1.5 dB of each other.

Figure 10. Comparison of noise readings taken at the output of a power divider with a true r.m.s. voltmeter and a spectrum analyzer.

Table 2. EMC Survey Test Data

Frequency	2.5	5	7.5	10	20	30
Fa(*), Quiet	53.6	44.9	39.7	36.1	27.3	22.2
Fa(*), QRA	42.2	33.6	28.6	25.0	16.4	11.4
En(Quiet)	0.8	-1.9	-3.5	-4.6	-7.4	-9.0
En(QRA)	-10.6	-13.1	-14.7	-15.7	-18.3	-19.8
US #1, Suburban Site, Aug 1997						
Fa(*)	55.6	42.1	33.0	28.7	16.0	12.1
Fa(Mon)	32.2	28.0	23.9	22.3	18.0	12.3
En(max)	6.9	-1.2	-9.3	-8.9	-16.9	-18.0
En(med)	-0.8	-7.7	-10.2	-12.4	-19.6	-19.1
En(min)	-6.0	-12.6	-13.3	-13.8	-20.9	-21.5
ASIA 1, Suburban Site, Nov 1997						
Fa(*)	48.2	33.7	27.0	24.9	17.4	14.1
Fa(Mon)	26.6	20.9	18.6	18.1	17.4	12.5
En(max)	-0.1	0.9	1.5	1.0	-12.1	-13.7
En(med)	-4.4	-12.8	-15.9	-15.5	-16.9	-16.5
En(min)	-7.5	-16.2	-20.5	-17.9	-20.0	-18.9
ASIA #2 Suburban Site, June 1997						
Fa(*)	53.0	42.3	35.2	35.5	19.9	19.0
Fa(Mon)	28.9	29.0	28.2	29.6	20.4	19.0
En(max)	9.7	0.1	-4.1	0.3	-9.1	-7.4
En(med)	0.3	-4.4	-8.0	-5.2	-14.8	-12.2
En(min)	-3.7	-9.0	-12.2	-11.1	-17.6	-19.4
ASIA 3, Rural, Sep 99						
Fa(*)	54.9	47.4	41.8	32.0	19.3	18.3
Fa(Mon)	31.7	33.0	32.5	25.3	19.2	13.6
En(max)	4.0	2.5	1.3	-6.5	-13.4	-10.9
En(med)	2.1	0.6	-1.7	-8.7	-15.4	-13.1
En(min)	0.2	-1.1	-7.5	-10.8	-17.5	-14.2
EU 1, Sep 1997						
Fa(*)	53.1	41.2	40.4	37.3	21.4	22.3
Fa(Mon)	28.2	27.0	32.9	31.1	21.6	20.4
En(max)	2.3	-3.5	-0.6	-2.8	-12.8	-8.3
En(med)	0.3	-5.6	-2.9	-3.4	-13.3	-8.9
En(min)	-1.9	-6.6	-4.1	-5.7	-13.7	-10.0

Note: Bandwidth is 3 kHz for En, 1 Hz for Fa.

Site EMC Protection Limit

A by product of the study presented above is the realization that En could be used as a site specific protection limit or guideline at which new devices being installed near a site must follow in order to achieve electromagnetic compatibility. For example,

unintentional emitters meeting commercial EMC standards could be shielded or not allowed to be installed unless separated from the antennas by a minimum distance [8]. At frequencies below 30 MHz, standards specify conducted noise emissions [9], but these limits could be translated into electric field values using the following equation [10]:

$$E_c = I_c + 20\text{Log}(F_{\text{MHz}}) - 20\text{Log}(d) + 20\text{Log}(l_c) - 4.041 \quad (14)$$

where E_c is the electric field magnitude in dB μ V/m caused by a conducted noise current I_c dB μ A, flowing in a conductor of vector length l_c meters and located d meters away. Figure 11 below shows the calculated electric field emanating from devices meeting U.S. EMC standards, if the conductor has a vector length of 2 meters. This length is consistent with electrical wiring in a one story house and the fields are expected if the housing structure provides no shielding.

Figure 11. Radiated noise calculated from U.S. conducted noise standards.

Conclusion

Presented in this paper is a process for measuring the ground wave gain, ground wave antenna factor, site noise electric field, and antenna noise factor of operational HF monopole antenna arrays. The process employs modern, swept-frequency instruments like spectrum analyzers equipped with tracking generators and RF network analyzers. These instruments were equivalent in performance to manual r.m.s. electric field intensity meters, but were easier to use in signals rich environments.

The results illustrate that while antenna noise factor F_a is very important for determining antenna-specific performance, the noise electric field intensity E_n may be a more useful parameter for comparing the performance of several sites. Published F_a is valid only for 9-ft rod antennas and may not apply to the performance of operational antennas. However, E_n can always be used to calculate the F_a of an antenna if either the G_{gw} , or AF_{gw} is known. Additionally, E_n can also be used as a site specific limit for defining electromagnetic compatibility between unintentional emitters and a site antenna array.

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